

Weather Forecasting

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Abstract

Weather forecasting is the application of science and technology to forecast the weather in a specific location. It is one of the world's most challenging problems. In this paper we are reviewing the various research paper to know the different types of technique, methods and algorithm are used to predict the weather.

Introduction

One of the hardest tasks for modern computers has always been predicting weather and for a good reason. Compared to the previous decades, we have progressed a ton in weather forecasting technology, but we are still miles away from achieving 100% accuracy. As one wise man said- In weather forecasting, we have to assume that we are wrong and our goal is be less wrong every time.

In simple terms, weather forecasting is the science of predicting weather of a certain place at a certain time by observing existing weather conditions. Although there are probably more than a million conditions that affect weather, we tend to focus on the major ones like temperature, clouds, wind speed, humidity, and past weather patterns.

Now, it's not illogical to ask what is the need for weather forecasting? But once you look at the property and human loss caused by weather

conditions such as tsunami, drought, and, rain , the urgency to predict weather falls into place.

Significance of Weather forecasting

1. Farming:

Farming is the major prey of faulty weather forecasts. Every year in India, thousands of farmers struggle, get in a debt-trap, and commit suicide because weather ruined their crops. Only if we were somehow predict weather with accuracy, those farmers would have lived.

2. Natural Calamities:

Every year, we hear news of floods and Hurricanes destroying major human hubs like Chennai and Orissa. The loss of property and life in these situations is immeasurable.

3. Early Rains:

The amount of resources we can save by predicting early rains is massive. Farmers can prepare crops at time, rain water harvesting plants can be set up, and big events can be delayed before huge investment is made.

Why it's so tough to predict weather?

The only thing that makes weather forecasting insanely difficult is mining the amount of data available.

Even though there are countless techniques that are used to mine the data from atmosphere, none of them are enough. Additionally, we can not mine future's data without creating a big error margin.

That is why today's meteorologists can only predict weather of up to 7 days and that too with only somewhat accuracy. Remember, you didn't take umbrella with you because your weather calendar said it won't rain?

But it did rain, and you stood in the middle of road with no umbrella.

Regardless, it's fine to trust weather forecast of a few upcoming days. But, after 7 days the predictions start becoming more and more wrong.

Techniques used for Weather Forecasting

Over the years, meteorologists have worked on numerous methods and techniques that can be used to predict the weather. Some of the popular methods include, but not limited to:

- Neural network-based algorithm utilizing Back Propagation Neural Network (BPN) and Hopfield Network
- Sprint Algorithm
- Recurrence Neural Network (RNN), Conditional Restricted Boltzmann Machine (CRBM)
- Artificial Neural Network and Decision tree Algorithms

- Predictive analysis in Apache Hadoop Framework utilizing Naive Bayes Algorithm
- Artificial Intelligent models

1. Back Propagation Neural Network and Hopfield Network

In simple terms, BPN is about understanding the dependency of cost function on weights and biases.

In other words:

BPN explains that changing biases and weights in a network causes a change in the cost function.

Typically, BPN works fairly well for initial modeling, and the outcomes obtained are sustained to a Hopfield Network. The Hopfield Network displays the work obtained by BPN with the help of training data set.

Hybrid back propagation based genetic algorithm approach is a popular way to train neural networks for weather prediction. The major drawback of this method is that weather parameters were assumed to be independent of each other and their temporal relation with one another was not considered. So in the present research a modified time series based weather prediction model is proposed to eliminate the problems incurred in hybrid BP/GA technique. The results are very encouraging; the proposed temporal weather prediction model outperforms the previous models while performing for dynamic and chaotic weather conditions.

searching is considered. It is good at global search (not in one direction) and it works with a

population of points instead of a single point. Also it blends the merits of both deterministic gradient based algorithm BP and stochastic optimizing algorithm GA. By using local gradient information advantageously, the hybrid technique is more speed efficient than GA. Hence the use of time series based hybrid BP/GA technique is proposed for weather prediction.

2. Sprint Algorithm

SPRINT algorithm, a concept of Decision Tree which represent the data in a tree structure. The salient feature of using the proposed SPRINT algorithm is it made the classification very early. On comparison to other algorithms, SPRINT algorithm has some salient features along with improvable measures which are best resembles in cloud technology. At the handling of massive data can be achieved by employing cloud computing. This is the key term for the evolution of SPRINT algorithm in this research work. As said decision tree is a tree structure and its extension SPRINT algorithm is also states the data in a tree structure.

The sample dataset from root to top several data are structured based on the relationship. According to the result, the sample data is split into several subsets and each subset has

a child nodes. This tree structure is formed as per the classification rule such as on what condition the result obtained. Generally, there are two phases in decision tree algorithms such as tree construction and tree pruning stage. On tree structure, leaf and child nodes form by recursively calling the classification algorithm. Tree pruning phase is responsible for cutting the unwanted branches that is irrelevant data. Our proposed SPRINT algorithm has two data structures such as attribute table and histogram. There are three parts in the property sheet namely attribute value, class identification, the

index of data records. In the memory all the data cannot be stored instead in the hard disc list of attributes can be stored. Attributes are divided with node expansion and linked to the respective child nodes. To demonstrate the attribute node distribution type the histogram is attached to nodes. There are two histograms such as Cbelow and Cabove. Initially, the sample type and its distribution are described, then untreated samples distribution type and finally the updated output of these two operations. On the SPRINT algorithm, the pruning is done using applying the minimum description length principle

3. Recurrence Neural Network and Conditional Restricted Boltzmann Machine

These two methods- RNN and CRBM are designed to test the capability of profound learning techniques when used for weather forecasting.

4. Apache Hadoop Framework utilizing Naive Bayes Algorithm

As explained earlier, predicting rainfall or early rainfall can be highly beneficial for certain niches, and that is accomplished by this model via utilizing predictive analysis in Hadoop.

These models (predictive analysis) are used to find out connections among elements in a dataset. This is done in order to find out the chance with a certain arrangement of conditions to allocate a score or weight.

5. Artificial Intelligent Models

With A.I. taking over everything, weather forecasting is no exception. In recent times, these models are proven to be more concentrated, effective, and right than typical statistical models. The reason for their superiority and better weather forecasting performance is that they are able to deal with non-linear datasets effectively.

Artificial Intelligent Models can be further classified into:

- Machine learning predators
- Deep learning predators

Related work

Chen and Wang (2000) proposed temperature prediction using fuzzy time series. The primary goal of this implementation is the overcoming of forecasting problems from the historical data. In this paper, the author handles the forecasting problems with two-factor time-variant fuzzy time series model. The outcome of this approach gained good forecasting results.

Maqsood et al (2004) proposed an ensemble of neural networks for weather forecasting. In this work, the author presented a comparison works of an ensemble of artificial neural networks (ANNs). For this, the major parameters taken for evaluation are data of temperature, wind speed, and relative humidity. The methodology used for this experiment is Hopfield model (HFM) predictive models, Elman recurrent neural network (ERNN), radial basis function network (RBFN), multi-layered perceptron network (MLPN) and regression techniques. The

comparison results show comparing to others RBFN is fair in dealing with weather forecasting problem whether HFM obtained less accurate performance.

Salman et al (2015) proposed Weather forecasting using deep learning techniques. The main objective of this work is exploring the hidden hierarchical pattern from the weather dataset. For the experiment, the author taken the weather dataset provided by BMKG (Indonesian Agency for Meteorology, Climatology, and Geophysics). This dataset undergoes with an observation of Recurrence Neural Network (RNN), Conditional Restricted Boltzmann Machine (CRBM), and Convolutional Network (CN) models. The obtained results predict weather forecast effectively and helpful for agriculture and tourism in a quiet manner.

Taksande et al. (2015) proposed Weather Forecasting Using Frequent Pattern Growth Algorithm. The main aim of this work is rainfall prediction. For this, the author took five years dataset from Jan 2010–Jan 2014 for Nagpur station and processed in Frequent Pattern Growth Algorithm. The rainfall prediction is based on the parameters such as temperature, humidity and wind speed. On this observation, about 90% is attained.

Wang et al. (2017) proposed Weather Forecast Using Data Mining Research Based on Cloud Computing. The author conducted his experiment with meteorological data collected in Specific time and applies Artificial Neural Network as well as Decision tree Algorithms for observation. The obtained result proves that the proposed methodology works effective mean weather variables with generating classification rules and results in a good outcome on weather forecasting

Sushmitha Kothapalli et al. (2017) proposed Real-Time Weather Forecasting and Analysis using Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), model. In this experiment, the author has taken the dataset with information like temperature, wind, humidity, and rainfall. These collected data are stored in the cloud as CSV, JSON, and XML file formats. The ARIMA model with correlation analysis on the parameters results in better prediction on weather forecasting.

Munmun et al. (2018) proposed Weather Forecast Prediction using an Integrated Approach for Analyzing and Measuring Weather Data. In this work, the author predicts the weather utilizing predictive analysis. For classification, Naive Bayes and Chi-square algorithm are applied. The weather forecasting is stated by a web application in which the user input some information's like current outlook, temperature, humidity and wind condition. According to the input, the system predicts the weather.

Conclusion

In conclusion, weather predictions are becoming more precise and valuable, and their advantages are spreading across the economy. While significant progress has been made in improving weather forecasts, there is still more to be done. Multiple stakeholders are working closely with the forecasting community to ensure that forecasts and alerts fulfil their unique needs. Simultaneously, they are building new technologies and observational networks that will help forecasters improve their skills and increase the value of their services to their customers.

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